

OPINIONS OF WESTERN SCIENTISTS ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MENTAL DEVELOPMENT AND EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14577763>

Abstract. *The article highlights the views of Western scientists on the relationship between mental development and education. It is substantiated that different stages of training depend on the specific age at which the child's psychological abilities mature, in any conditions, even in the most favorable conditions of training and education, at the level of development, various mental signs, functions and personality traits are manifested.*

Key words: *mental development, education, function, character, development, level, ideas, process, thinking.*

МНЕНИЯ ЗАПАДНЫХ УЧЕНЫХ О ВЗАИМОСВЯЗИ ПСИХИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. *В статье освещаются взгляды западных ученых о взаимосвязи психического развития и образования. Обосновано, что разные этапы обучения зависят от конкретного возраста, в котором созревают психологические способности ребенка, в любых условиях, даже в самых благоприятных условиях обучения и воспитания, на уровне развития проявляются различные психические признаки, функции и свойства личности.*

Ключевые слова: *психическое развитие, образование, функция, характер, развитие, уровень, идеи, процесс, мышление.*

INTRODUCTION

Hurriyat demands that rich spirituality and spiritual science be used rationally, fairly and effectively. All existing educational institutions of our country should know the specific psychological patterns of this process, its mechanisms, as well as effective methods for creating an active, independent and positive thought process based on modern knowledge, for organizing education on a scientific basis. The science of psychology, relying on modern theory, explains the composition of the human personality, based on the data that it mainly depends on the influence of three factors. The first of them is the influence of the external social environment in which a person is born and grows up, the second is the influence of education and upbringing, regularly given to a person over a long period of time, and the third is the effect of genetic features that are given to a person from birth, ready.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

The environment, education and appropriate exercises help to structure the brain organically. What is the role of education in this process? Does education play a leading role in development or vice versa? The solution to this problem determines the content and methodology of the educational process, the content of educational programs and textbooks. For example, the German psychologist V. Stern put forward the idea that education follows mental development and adapts to it. Contrary to this opinion, the Russian psychologist L. S. Vygotsky was the first to put forward the rule that training and upbringing play a leading role in the mental development of a child, and said: education precedes development and follows it. clearly states that it will go.

According to the first idea outlined above, education uses only what is achieved by development. Therefore, it is necessary not to interfere with the process of intellectual maturation, not to destroy it, but to patiently and passively wait until the opportunity for education appears.

The theory of the Swiss psychologist J. Piaget was also based on these ideas.

According to J. Piaget, the mental development of a child and a schoolchild develops on the basis of its own internal laws and goes through a number of qualitatively unique genetic stages.

Education can only speed up or slow down the process of mental maturation, but cannot have a serious impact on the process of mental maturation. Therefore, education must obey the laws of development. For example, it is useless to teach a child to think logically without developing logical thinking. It follows that the different stages of education depend on the specific age at which the child's psychological abilities mature. We believe that education plays a leading role and that education and development are interdependent; these are not two separate processes, but one whole process. Without education, there can be no full-fledged mental development.

Education stimulates development, and development follows it. When the necessary conditions arise, education develops logical thinking skills and becomes the basis for the corresponding intellectual development. But education, stimulating development, relies on development itself, takes into account the peculiarities of the achieved level of development, the internal rules of development, of course. Although the possibilities of education are very broad, they are not unlimited. The great Russian psychologist L.S. Vygotsky approached the problem of education and development from the point of view of the socio-historical process. It is argued that appropriation is a process of participation of culture created in the historical development of mankind. According to the cultural-historical theory of the development of mental functions put forward by him, it is understood that the development of mental activity directly reconstructs its "natural" form, taking its external and then internal expression with various symptoms, acquiring a "cultural" form. form.Hurriyat demands that rich spirituality and spiritual science be used rationally, fairly and effectively. All existing educational institutions of our country should know

the specific psychological patterns of this process, its mechanisms, as well as effective methods for creating an active, independent and positive thought process based on modern knowledge, for organizing education on a scientific basis. The science of psychology, based on modern theory, explains the composition of the human personality, based on the data that it mainly depends on the influence of three factors. The first of them is the influence of the external social environment in which a person is born and grows up, the second is the influence of education and upbringing regularly given to a person over a long period of time, and the third is the effect of genetic features that are given to a person from birth, ready. The environment, education and appropriate exercises help to structure the brain organically. What is the role of education in this process? Does education play a leading role in development or vice versa? The solution to this problem determines the content and methodology of the educational process, the content of educational programs and textbooks. For example, the German psychologist V. Stern put forward the idea that education follows mental development and adapts to it. Contrary to this opinion, the Russian psychologist L. S. Vygotsky was the first to put forward the rule that training and upbringing play a leading role in the mental development of a child, and said: education precedes development and follows it. clearly states that it will go. According to the first idea stated above, education uses only what is achieved by development. Therefore, it is necessary not to interfere with the process of intellectual maturation, not to destroy it, but to patiently and passively wait until the opportunity for education appears. The theory of the Swiss psychologist J. Piaget was also based on these ideas. According to J. Piaget, the mental development of a child and a schoolchild develops on the basis of its own internal laws and goes through a number of qualitatively unique genetic stages. Education can only speed up or slow down the process of mental maturation, but it cannot have a serious impact on the process of mental maturation. Therefore, education must obey the laws of development. For example, it is useless to teach a child to think logically without developing logical thinking. It follows that the different stages of education depend on the specific age at which the child's psychological abilities mature. We believe that education plays a leading role and that education and development are interdependent; they are not two separate processes, but one whole process.

Without education, there can be no full-fledged mental development. Education stimulates development, and development follows it. When the necessary conditions arise, education develops logical thinking skills and becomes the basis for the corresponding intellectual development. But education, stimulating development, relies on development itself, takes into account the features of the achieved level of development, the internal rules of development, of course. Although the possibilities of education are very broad, they are not unlimited.

CONCLUSION

Psychologists note that there are general laws of mental development. However, these laws are secondary in relation to the influence of the environment, since the specific characteristics of these laws depend on the conditions of life, activity and education. Mann, such general laws include, first of all, the unevenness of mental development. The essence of this is that in any conditions, even in the most favorable conditions of education and upbringing, various mental signs, functions and characteristics of a person do not stop at the bit level of development. In certain periods of a child's development, extremely favorable conditions for the development of the psyche in one direction or another are formed, and some of these conditions are temporary, transient.

Such age periods, which are the most favorable conditions for the development of certain mental characteristics and qualities, are called sensitive periods. (L. S. Vygotsky, A. N. Leontiev). the existence of a sensitivity period is due to the regularity of organic maturation of the brain, some mental processes and characteristics, life experience. Thus, the mental development of a child or schoolchild is a complex development process.

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